

BUSINESS PROCESS ANALYSIS AND QUALITY CONTROL USING SIX SIGMA AND DMAIC

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Abstract

The rapidly increasing technology are accompanied by increasing competition in the industrial world. The pharmaceutical industry is one industry that has a high level of competition. The solution to remain competitive is to improve the quality in the industrial sector and utilize technological developments in its business processes. One of the pharmaceutical industries in Indonesia is PT. XYZ. In its business process, PT. XYZ has not carried out maximum quality control, thus there are still defective products produced. In addition, the process of material flow from the beginning to the finished product has not utilized technology optimally, such as inputting the number of defective products that is done manually. The purpose of this research is to find out the sigma value of the company and analyze business processes that produce the most defective products. The quality control method used is Six Sigma and the DMAIC concept. The type of defect produced by PT. XYZ is the leaky ampoule, taper ampoule and there are remaining particles. Based on the analysis of the entire production process, there are three production processes that produce product defects, namely washing, filling and viewing processes. Based on calculations with the Six Sigma method, the DPMO value is 5,766.66 and the acquisition of sigma value is 4.1.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the industrial world is increasing with intense competition (Mubarak, 2015). Every existing company must be able to maintain and improve the effectiveness and efficiency that exists with the aim of a company to remain competitive and competent (Abbas, 2009). Quality is the most fundamental thing from customer satisfaction and success in competing. The higher the level of product quality given to consumers, the higher the level of consumer needs will be fulfilled so that customer satisfaction will increase. Product quality can be used as a comprehensive evaluation of customers for the good of goods or services (Mowen, John, & Michael, 2002).

Many industries have not paid attention to quality control on the products they produce so that they still produce defects in products. This can reduce the level of loyalty from consumers if it is not handled specifically. So in this case there is a need for quality control in every industry. The pharmaceutical industry is definitely required to be able to produce drugs that meet the efficacy, safety and quality in doses used for medicinal purposes. Therefore, pharmaceutical companies are expected not to make a mistake in the production process which can affect the quality of medicines that will be produced in the production process.

Six Sigma is a quality control method. With its DMAIC concept, the Six Sigma method strives to achieve zero failure rates. The DMAIC concept known as the define, measure, analyze, improve and control cycles is expected to reduce the number of defects (Satrijo, Sari, & Hidayat, 2013).

This research was conducted at PT. XYZ to find out the quality of the product and the type of defect produced. In addition, using the Cause and Effect to determine the cause of the defect so that it can provide suggestions for improvement to improve the quality of the product.

Figure 1. Total Production and Total Good Product

Based on the data that has been obtained, there is a comparison between the total production and the total good products for sale.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Collecting and Type of Data

Data collection was carried out including preliminary surveys to obtain preliminary information about existing problems and collect the data needed to be analyzed. Next is to study literature to study the literature related to research. Then the field study was carried out by directly observing the production process of PT. XYZ to obtain data needed in research. The techniques used in field studies include observation, documentation, and interviews. Observation is done by analyzing problems and collecting data through direct observation in the production process. Documentation is carried out to collect data related to existing problems. While interviews are conducted directly with respondents who are related to obtain data related to company problems, so that it can be used to identify the main factors that cause defects.

2.2 Data Processing Method

The data that has been obtained from the results of observations and interviews is processed using the Six Sigma method, DMAIC Concept, Control Chart, and Fishbone Diagram to determine the sigma value and the causes of product defects PT. XYZ

2.1.1 Six Sigma

In the production process there are always defective products, such as in the injection production section of PT. XYZ. which produces more defective products so that it can cause losses to the company. In this case quality control methods are needed such as the Six Sigma method to determine the value of the quality of the product produced. Six Sigma merupakan konsep statistik yang mengukur suatu proses yang berkaitan dengan cacat atau kerusakan. Six Sigma is a method of quality control towards the target of 3.4 failures per one million

opportunities for every transaction of a product or service, in other words that the process runs almost perfectly (Gaspersz, 2005). Six Sigma as a measurement system using Defect per Million Opportunities (DPMO) as a unit of measurement. DPMO is a good measure for product quality or process, because it correlates directly with defects, costs and time wasted.

Table 1. Relationship between Sigma and DPMO values

Sigma	Parts per Million
6 Sigma	3,4 defects per million
5 Sigma	233 defects per million
4 Sigma	6.210 defects per million
3 Sigma	66.807 defects per million
2 Sigma	308. 357 defects per million
1 Sigma	690.000 defects per million

Source: Gaspersz, V (2002)

2.1.2 DMAIC Concept

Six Sigma uses a statistical tool to identify several factors. DMAIC is a method in measuring sigma values for continuous quality improvement to achieve the Six Sigma value target which consists of define, measure, analysis, improve and control (Wahyani et al, 2013). In the define stage, identification of the production process at the injection work station is based on the production sequence. Then continued the measure step which is a measurement process of the previous process (basic measurement), which aims to evaluate based on existing goals. In this step information or data is collected. Some of the tools used in this step include using control charts, data collection forms, flow diagrams, pareto diagrams, scatter diagrams, frequency plots. After that, in the analysis phase an analysis of the causes of product defects is carried out by using a fishbone diagram. Improve is an improvement effort so that the number of defects is reduced and the quality of the product will be better. The last stage is the control stage, it is expected that PT. XYZ can periodically check the production process. In addition, so that product quality can be improved is by doing a periodic evaluation and improvement.

2.1.3 Control Chart

Control Chart is one of the tools used by production to control the production process statistically or better known as Statistical Process Control (SPC) that is by determining how much the level of product damage that the company can accept (Khomah & Rahayu, 2012). Control Chart is also one of the tools of 7 Quality Control Tools (QC 7 Tools) that are well known.

2.1.4 Research Flow

To answer the research question, the research was conducted through several stages. Below is a description of the research flow with a flowchart diagram.

Figure 2 Research Flow

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this case, quality control methods such as the Six Sigma method are needed to determine the value of the quality of products produced which are integrated with the DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, Control) method.

3.1 Define

The business process of processing injection medicine are washing, mixing, filling, viewing, checking and packing. The process that can cause product defects is the washing process of ampoule (washing), filling (filling) and checking with Brevetti (viewing).

3.2 Measure

Products produced from the initial production process to the end of production produce several defective products. The types of defects produced are as follows:

Table 2 Defect Type

No	Defect Type	Count
1	Leaky ampoule	10041
2	There are remaining particles	21569
3	Taper ampoule	4946

Figure 3 Pareto Chart

The following is the result of the sigma value obtained:
Calculate total defects per unit (DPU) and DPMO

$$DPU = \frac{36556}{2110798}$$

$$DPU = 0,0173$$

$$DPMO = \frac{0,0173 \times 1.000.000}{3}$$

$$DPMO = 5.766,66$$

Based on the results of the DPMO, the DMPO was 5,766.66, so the sigma value was 4.1 which meant that PT. XYZ already has a fairly good quality and average USA industry. However, despite producing sigma values that are good enough, the production process has not run stably.

Figure 4 Defect Product Chart

3.4 Analyze

At this stage, analyze the causes of product defects. The cause of leaky ampoules is the engine setting error, the sealing is too tight, the product transfer method is too far, the product arrangement is piled up, the environment is damp, and the workforce is less skilled. In particle defects caused by engine factors, due to errors when the engine settings and fire are too large, and the workforce is less skilled. At the taper ampoule of the engine factor, because of an error when the engine setting and fire are too large, and the workforce is less skilled.

3.5 Improve

Improve what you have to do is the need to have the machine setting SOP, specify the maximum standard in the sealing AVR machine, scheduling, increase security during the production process and provide training.

3.6 Control

The last stage is the control stage, it is expected that PT. XYZ can periodically check the production process. In addition, so that product quality can be improved is by periodic evaluation and improvement.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of product quality research carried out produced several conclusions as follows:

1. The sigma value obtained is 4.1 which is quite good.
2. The type of defect that occurs is the product leaking, there is a foreign object in the injection product and a taper ampoule.
3. The cause of product defects can be caused by several factors such as human, machine, environment and methods. Improvements to the RUR machine, AVR, Brevetti by forming engine speed guidelines to comply with applicable standards, machine maintenance (preventive maintenance), transfer of goods through a pass through so that the transportation process is not too far away and determines the maximum capacity in product accumulation

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